

major diseases. Diversifying rice varieties is crucial in controlling these diseases.

We compared 24 varieties, with four replications each, Oct 1987-May 1988 at five sites representative of Burundi's swamp environmental types (see table).

Temperatures below 15°C were aggregated during three stages: transplanting to booting, booting to flowering, and during maturation. We evaluated BSR and BI on the mature tillers of 10 plants randomly selected from each plot.

The Muramba site benefited most from favorable climate (see table). At Ndebe, the temperature frequently dropped below 15°C. Temperatures were lowest during tillering (Jan to mid-Feb) but rose progressively until maturity (mid-Mar to end Apr).

Cultivation type and BSR and BI severity at 5 Burundi sites.

Site	Altitude (m)	Cultivation type	Disease severity ^a		Hours (no.) of temp below 15°C		
			BSR	BI	Tillering	Booting	Maturation
Akagoma 1	1560	Groundwater	11.5	1.9	414	119	49
Akagoma 2	1560	Flooded	37.1	7.8	414	119	49
Kobero	1390	Flooded	5.3	20.0	109	68	23
Muramba	1370	Groundwater	6.3	4.9	9	6	4
Ndebe	1540	Flooded	6.1	2.7	564	251	199

^aMean of 24 varieties (%) scored by these scales: BSR — 0 = panicles correctly emerged, 1 = less than 1/3 of panicle blocked, 2 = 1/3 - 2/3 of panicle blocked, 3 = more than 2/3 of panicle blocked. BI — 0 = healthy panicles; 1 = blackened neck, less than 1/3 unfilled grains; 2 = blackened neck, 1/3 - 2/3 unfilled grains; 3 = blackened neck, more than 2/3 unfilled grains.

$$\text{Severity coefficient} = 3 \times \frac{\text{sum of scores}}{\text{number of tillers}} \times 100$$

BSR developed after booting, when the bacteria tend to multiply rapidly. The severity coefficient of blocked panicles was highest (37.1%) at Akagoma 2 and moderate at Ndebe.

We noted BI on leaves during tillering, except at Akagoma 2 and Ndebe, where it

appeared during booting. Nodal BI at maturity was most severe at Kobero.

The climatic parameters noted do not sufficiently explain the severity of BSR and BI incidence. Future studies need to measure temperature, relative humidity in the leaf areas, and soil fertility.

Efficacy of *Beauveria bassiana* combined with various stickers or spreaders against rice hispa (RH)

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RH *Dicladispa armigera* Olivier (Coleoptera, Chrysomelidae) attacks summer rice in areas around Assam with high relative humidity and average rainfall of 2,500-4,500 mm. An effective biocontrol agent is *B. bassiana* (Bals.) Vuill, but it is not practical to apply conidial suspen-

sions to large fields because of heavy rains.

We evaluated efficacy of *B. bassiana* combined with some stickers and spreaders for RH control.

Conidial suspensions (1×10^7 conidia/ml) were mixed separately with Sandovit (Agril. wetting agent), Triton-AE (universal spreader sticker), Teepol B-300 (liquid detergent), Tween 80, and Hamam toilet soap, all at 0.23 g/liter concentration.

We used an atomizer with 6 ml of the suspension on rice seedlings in plastic pots. The seedlings were air-dried 30

min, then confined with 20 RH adults (4 d old) that had been starved for 6 h.

Sticker/spreader treatments in water were dispensed four times until runoff at 8-h intervals for 5 d. Seedlings sprayed with water mixed with stickers and spreaders without *B. bassiana* served as control.

Mortality percentages were recorded on the 10th day after inoculation. In the control, adult deaths were around 10% (see table).

Tween 80 and Hamam were the best compatible sticker/spreader with *B. bassiana* against RH. □

Effect of *B. bassiana* mixed with different stickers and spreaders on rice hispa adults.

Treatment	Mortality (%) ^a
Water + <i>B. bassiana</i>	51.89 (46.06)
Teepol + <i>B. bassiana</i>	81.48 (64.48)
Triton-AE + <i>B. bassiana</i>	74.08 (59.40)
Tween 80 + <i>B. bassiana</i>	96.30 (79.30)
Sandovit + <i>B. bassiana</i>	81.48 (64.55)
Hamam + <i>B. bassiana</i>	93.26 (75.03)
LSD (0.05)	3.84
(0.01)	5.32

^aData in parentheses represent angular transformed values which were analyzed.

Integrated pest management—insects

Mating sequence of rice leaffolder (LF) *Marasmia patnalis* Bradley

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The mating sequence of the 3- to 4-d-old LF under a reversed cycle—12 h scotophase, 12 h photophase—served as basis for a bioassay of identified sex pheromone compounds. Forty same-age pairs were observed.

Mating activities in *M. patnalis* commenced when the females assumed

the calling position: curving the abdomen dorsally and expanding the wings (see figure, a). The responsive male engaged in random flight, and vigorous antenna and wing vibration (figure, b). The male approached the calling female and tapped her wings with his antennae and foretarsi during courtship (figure, c).

The male then attempted copulation by approaching the female from behind (figure, d). Placing his antennae and foretarsi on the female's wings, he extruded his clasper and curved his abdomen ventrally until the clasper touched the female's abdominal tip